

A short note on total iron estimation in ilmenite sample by wet chemical technique

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Abstract : A wet chemical method of total iron estimation in ilmenite sample has been reported. The method is fast, accurate, economic, analyst friendly and compares well with the existing methods. It does not require silica separation prior to iron estimation.

Keywords : Ilmenite, total iron, analysis, wet chemical.

Introduction

Existing wet chemical method of total iron estimation in ilmenite involves sample opening with potassium pyrosulphate, followed by its extraction with 1 : 1 H₂SO₄. Silica in the residue is removed through hydrofluoridation. Once silica is separated total iron is estimated through R₂O₃ separation and standard dichromate titration¹. Alternatively, ilmenite sample may be fused with Na₂CO₃ and borax and melt is extracted with 1 : 1 H₂SO₄ and analysed by ICP-OES for total iron. This method was developed originally for estimation of total iron in iron ores².

While conventional wet chemical method is time consuming and requires large number of chemicals including hydrofluoric acid, ICP-OES method is plagued with high salt content in the analytical solution. It has been observed that Na₂CO₃-Borax-ICP method is not suitable for high silica samples. Also, ICP-OES method is cost prohibitive when number of samples is low.

An alternative scheme of total iron estimation in ilmenite has been provided in the present report where sample is opened with KHSO₄ and the melt is extracted with 1 : 1 H₂SO₄. Total iron in the extract has been estimated using conventional dichromate titration without separating silica.

This alternative technique provides several advantages over the existing methods.

Stepwise method details :

Step 1 : Ilmenite sample was ground to fine powder

(-200 mesh) from which about 0.1 g is accurately weighed and taken in a silica crucible for analysis.

Step 2 : The sample is thoroughly mixed with KHSO₄ (2-3 g) and heated in a burner at low temperature so as to melt it slowly.

Step 3 : Once the sample melts, it is kept in a muffle furnace for 5-10 min at 950 °C after which it is taken out of the furnace and allowed to cool at room temperature.

Step 4 : The crucible with its content is transferred to a beaker and extracted with 50 ml 1 : 1 H₂SO₄. Once the fused mass is completely extracted, the crucible is removed and washed with 1 : 1 H₂SO₄.

Step 5 : 25 ml HCl is added to the solution in the beaker and heated over a hot plate for 15-20 min till the solution becomes clear.

Step 6 : Iron content in the solution is estimated by standard dichromate titration using BDS indicator.

Results and discussion

Total iron in a number of ilmenite samples was estimated using the reported as well as ICP method, results of which have been presented in Table 1. An ilmenite CRM (Dillinger Ilmenite 6704) was also analysed by both the techniques for the purpose of validation, results of which have also been presented in Table 1.

It may be seen that the reported method returns certified iron value of the CRM quite closely thus ensuring

Table 1. Comparison of total iron estimated in different ilmenite samples using the reported method and existing ICP technique

Sample	Total iron (%)	
	ICP technique	Reported technique
Ilmenite 1	5.23	5.34
Ilmenite 2	32.48	31.55
Ilmenite 3	4.50	4.34
Ilmenite 4	36.12	35.39
Ilmenite 5	39.89	39.29
Ilmenite 6	22.44	22.01
Ilmenite 7	36.80	36.61
Dillinger Ilmenite 6704 (Certified Fe value : 36.23%)		36.27

method validation. One may also find that the total iron in different ilmenite samples as obtained from the reported technique, match well with corresponding ICP results.

Advantages :

The reported method has several advantages over exist-

ing iron estimation technique in ilmenite which are listed below.

This is fast, accurate and reliable.

This is analyst and environment friendly as it does not use hydrofluoric acid.

Prior silica separation is not a prerequisite for iron estimation.

The method is economical.

Acknowledgement

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References

1. Manual of procedures for chemical and instrumental analysis of ores, minerals and ore dressing products by IBM, pp-163-165, January 1979.
2. In house method developed at CSIR-NML as a part of its NABL accreditation.